

With the support of the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Aix-Marseille University (FRANCE)
Tor Vergata University of Rome (ITALY)
Wrocław University of Science and Technology (POLAND)

Erasmus Mundus Joint Master's Degree in
Chemical NanoEngineering

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EXCITON DYNAMICS IN ORGANIC DYES: DPP AS A CASE STUDY

Thesis presented to obtain a master's degree.

Defended on 10/09/2024 in front of the jury.

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Abstract

In the pursuit of efficient solar energy harvesting, organic dyes have emerged as promising candidates. Among these, Diketopyrrolopyrroles (DPPs) have attracted significant interest due to their easy functionalization and favorable spectral redshifts. However, the molecular-level properties of DPPs remain insufficiently explored. In this study, we investigated the electronic structure and excited state dynamics of a DPP-core dimer to gain deeper insights into their photophysics. Unexpectedly, our findings reveal an energetically accessible conical intersection, which facilitates a highly efficient relaxation pathway. The internal conversion time constant was determined to be 0.4 ps, indicating a tiny fluorescence quantum yield. This conical intersection is driven by a hydrogen migration between the monomers, as confirmed by a wavefunction analysis. Therefore, careful functionalization of DPPs is crucial to suppress such internal conversion and enhance their performance in solar energy applications.

Acknowledgments

I would like to begin by expressing my deepest gratitude to the European Commission for their generous financial support and for granting me the invaluable opportunity to pursue my master's studies through the ERASMUS MUNDUS scholarship. I am also immensely thankful to the Institut de Chimie Radicalaire (ICR) for graciously hosting me during my master's internship.

My most profound appreciation goes to my thesis directors, Prof. Mario BARBATTI and Dra. Josene M. TOLDO, for their exceptional mentorship and unwavering support. Under their guidance, my scientific curiosity has truly blossomed. Their insightful advice and constructive feedback have been instrumental in shaping the course of my research. To Mario and Josene, I am very honored and grateful to be your student—thank you both for everything!

To my beloved family—my mother Ekhlas, my father Abdullah, my dear brother Mohammed, and my cherished sister Sageda—your unwavering love and support have been my greatest sources of strength throughout this journey. I am deeply thankful to have you in my life.

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1. Introduction

With the concerning increase in greenhouse gas emissions and their severe implications in worsening global warming, many efforts have been implemented to rely on renewable, clean energy sources such as wind energy, hydroelectric energy, and solar energy. Solar energy is the energy transferred from the sun in the form of electromagnetic radiation that is primarily abundant within the infrared and visible spectrum. It is recognized as one of the most promising technologies due to its sustainability and availability almost everywhere on the planet's surface. Nonetheless, the latest statistics¹ show that solar energy contributes to only 4.57% of global electricity production, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Global electricity production by source. Data source: Ember (2024); Energy Institute - Statistical Review of World Energy (2024) from Ref 1.

Even though the relative contribution of solar energy has been growing over the last few decades, it still falls behind the dominating fossil fuel energy resources. This is mainly due to their high capital investments and long payback periods. Currently, solar energy harvesting technologies include concentrating solar power technology,² space solar power stations,³ and photovoltaic (PV) Cells.⁴ PV cells have been shown to be the most suitable solar technology due to their robustness, decentralization, and relative affordability.

On the molecular level, PV technology, based on its excitation mechanism, can be divided into two main categories: crystalline semiconductors (CSCs) and excitonic semiconductors (XCSs).⁵ Nowadays, CSCs such as silicon technologies are the most used PV cells because of their higher efficiencies (~20-24%) and longer service times (20-25 years) compared to their XCS counterparts. However, the cost of SCS cells compared to their saturated efficiencies has limited their installation domestically rather than industrially.⁶ The only method believed to substantially boost the efficiency of CSCs is to use multi-chip (GaAs/Si technology), which introduces major technical (fabrication) and economic difficulties. Thus, researchers have been

motivated to investigate other PV technologies that could replace fossil fuels, such as excitonic semiconductors.⁷

XCSs have been a hot topic within the scientific community due to their promising capabilities, including high absorption coefficients, tunable absorption spectra, flexibility, and, most importantly, their low cost. Their big room for improvement is believed to overcome their current drawbacks, mainly their debatable efficiencies (could reach 19%) and their shorter service times due to their chemical instabilities.⁸

Unlike the simple electron-hole separation mechanism in crystalline semiconductors, exciton transport is not fully understood at the molecular level. An exciton is a quasi-particle in which the hole and the electron are in a bound state, as shown in Figure 2. These pairs are generated upon photon absorption of incident light. Excitonic materials have a low dielectric constant, which strengthens their electric field and increases their binding energy;⁸ hence, the electron-hole pairs do not spontaneously dissociate as in the case of silicon semiconductors. The exciton binding energy alongside the average distance of the electron-hole pair plays a vital role in the exciton lifetime.⁹

Thus, a solid interpretation of exciton transport is critical for optimizing the performance of excitonic semiconductors, which usually have a bottleneck of short exciton diffusion length. In fact, the main reason why excitonic solar cells (like organic solar cells) are so thin is that any increase in the thickness of the panel would, yes, increase the number of excitons generated. Still, those excitons would have to travel distances (to the electrodes) that are longer than their average diffusion length, making them completely unusable. For flat organic solar cells, the diffusion length is shorter than the light absorption length.⁸

Figure 2: Excitons at the orbital level.

With the ongoing improvements in chemical synthesis on organic solar cells, the questions about exciton transport are still not being answered, and relying on the primitive push-pull mechanism or the spreading of the wavefunction to an extended π - π -conjugation network is not sufficient.¹⁰ This is mainly due to the complex potential energy surfaces and the different relaxation pathways. Such dilemmas were also observed in other types of chemistry, such as coordination chemistry, where ruthenium coordination compounds showed much higher photocatalytic properties than their iron counterparts, even though ruthenium and iron have the same number of electrons in the outmost shell.¹¹ Moreover, the excited states of organic molecules are not as well separated as the separation between the ground state and the first

excited state, which results in multi-dimensional conical intersections and increases the complexity of excited state chemistry compared to ground state chemistry.

Fortunately, some theories have been developed to describe the energy transfer between chromophores and the rate of the transfer, such as Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET) by Theodor Förster in 1946,¹² as well as the Marcus theory by Rudolph A. Marcus in 1956.¹³ More recently, exciton single-singlet annihilation (SSA) has been explored to give a bigger picture of exciton dynamics.¹⁴

From a computational perspective, a static description of excited states would require a quantum treatment of the system's electron density since it is the only way where explicit electrons are considered. This has become feasible in the last few decades due to the accelerating microprocessing power, according to Moore's law.¹⁵ On the other hand, a full quantum description of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation is still unattainable. Thus, non-adiabatic dynamics has been proposed as an approach in which the electron wavefunction is quantumly treated, and their potentials are imposed in Newton's equations to mimic the movement of the nuclei.¹⁶ This mixed quantum-classical approach has become the most used¹⁷ for theoretical calculations in the field of computational photochemistry.

Initially, the goal of this master's thesis was to study exciton transport on organic dyes. However, after starting the dynamics with the core of a diketopyrrolopyrroles (DPP) dimer (a family of molecules known for their fluorescence), the highest percentage of trajectories were observed to relax to the ground state. Thus, the goal of this thesis was adjusted since studying the relaxation pathway of DPP dimers will definitely be beneficial for the community as it underlines the importance of functionalization of the DPP-based devices. Hence, computational chemistry and non-adiabatic dynamics were used to describe different photochemical processes, and the refined goals of the master thesis are the follows:

- To investigate the different relaxation pathways and their influence on exciton dynamics using Newton-X, a program developed by Prof. Barbatti's group for non-adiabatic dynamics.
- To characterize the critical relaxation pathways in terms of charge transfer.
- To report the current challenges faced when studying singlet-singlet annihilation.

2. Background

Before we review the literature and methodology used in this project, it is essential first to cover some fundamentals of excited state chemistry and the computational methods used to investigate them. To do so, this chapter is dedicated to presenting key topics of quantum mechanics and discussing the methodologies used in this work. The electronic structure principles and methods, such as (TD)DFT, will be briefly presented. After that, nonadiabatic dynamics (Surface hopping method) will be discussed. Lastly, this chapter will summarize the different photochemical processes relevant in the context of DPPs.

2.1. Quantum Chemical Methods

2.1.1 Time-independent Schrödinger Equation

The time-independent Schrödinger equation (TISE), developed by Erwin Schrödinger in 1926, describes the wavefunction of a quantum mechanical system as a linear partial differential equation. TISE is an eigenvalue equation where the eigenvectors of the Hamiltonian operator correspond to the wavefunctions, and the associated eigenvalues represent the energy levels of the system and are quantized.¹⁸ Thus, TISE is written as in Equation 1.

$$\hat{H}\Psi = E\Psi \quad (1)$$

On a many-body system, the molecular Hamiltonian (neglecting external electromagnetic fields) can be expressed as:

$$\hat{H} = V_N + V_e + V_{NN} + V_{eN} + V_{ee} \quad (2)$$

where the first two terms are the kinetic energy operators of the nuclei and electrons, respectively, and the following three terms describe the potential energy operators representing the nucleus-nucleus, electron-nucleus, and electron-electron interactions, respectively. It is more convenient to write the expected value of the energy using the bracket notation introduced by Dirac as follows¹⁹:

$$\langle \Psi | H | \Psi \rangle = E \quad (3)$$

In this notation, $\langle \Psi |$ is called the bra, and $|\Psi \rangle$ is called the ket, which both are space vectors in the Hilbert space. These vector spaces have dimensionality N , a vector which is the maximal number of linearly independent vectors that span the whole space.¹⁹ If we denote $|\Psi_0 \rangle$ as the ground state vector, then the ground state eigenenergy would be:

$$\langle \Psi_0 | H | \Psi_0 \rangle = E_0 \quad (4)$$

where $\langle \Psi_1 | \Psi_2 \rangle$ defines the inner product, and it is equivalent to the dot product of the ket with the complex conjugate of the bra. The electron density of the ground state can be computed from $\langle \Psi_0 | \hat{\rho}(r) | \Psi_0 \rangle$ where r is a spatial variable.¹⁹

From a numerical perspective, there are some mathematical tricks we could use to evaluate the Schrödinger equation on a system, such as the Born-Oppenheimer approximation in which the electronic energies are computed for fixed nuclear positions, which enable us to invoke the electronic coordinates as independent variables and the nuclear positions as parameters for the SE. The implications of such approximation will be mentioned again in the non-adiabatic dynamics section of this report.

The wavefunction also can be constructed as a linear combination of one-electron wavefunctions (also known as set orbitals). This approach is called the Linear Combination of Atomic Orbitals (LCAO), and it is used alongside the variational principle to compute the state energies.²⁰ Thus, the wavefunction of a system can be written as:

$$\Phi = \sum_i c_i \Psi_i \quad (5)$$

The variational principle will not be derived here. Still, in simple words, it tells that the energies associated with wavefunction constructed from LCAO approximation will always have higher energy than the exact eigenvalue energy, as shown in

$$\langle \Phi | H | \Phi \rangle \geq E \quad (6)$$

The inaccuracy of this approximation is seen more in excited states than in the ground state. There is no guarantee that the corresponding trial wavefunction will tend to the actual wavefunction. Nevertheless, it defines a route to solve TISE numerically.

2.1.2 Hartree-Product Wavefunctions and Hartree Hamiltonian

Let us break down the Hamiltonian of a many-body system in equation 2 in a one-electron Hamiltonian, which comprises only the nuclear attraction and kinetic energy terms given as:

$$H = \sum_{i=1}^N h_i \quad (7)$$

where N is the total number of electrons in the system, and h_i is the one-electron Hamiltonian defined by:

$$h_i = -\frac{1}{2} \nabla_i^2 - \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{Z_k}{r_{ik}} \quad (8)$$

where M is the total number of nuclei, Z is the atomic number, and h_i is given in atomic units. Thus, there should be a corresponding one-electron wavefunction that must satisfy the Schrödinger equation as:

$$h_i \psi_i = \varepsilon_i \psi_i \quad (9)$$

Since we defined the Hamiltonian in equation 8 to be separable, the products of one-electron wavefunctions can be used to construct the many-body wavefunction as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_{\text{HP}} &= \psi_1 \psi_2 \cdots \psi_N & (10) \\ H \Psi_{\text{HP}} &= H \psi_1 \psi_2 \cdots \psi_N \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N h_i \psi_1 \psi_2 \cdots \psi_N \\ &= (h_1 \psi_1) \psi_2 \cdots \psi_N + \psi_1 (h_2 \psi_2) \cdots \psi_N + \cdots + \psi_1 \psi_2 \cdots (h_N \psi_N) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N \varepsilon_i \psi_1 \psi_2 \cdots \psi_N \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \varepsilon_i \right) \Psi_{\text{HP}} \end{aligned}$$

This implies that the energy eigenvalue of the many-electron wavefunction in this approximation is nothing but the sum of the individual energy eigenvalue of the one-electron wavefunctions.

Before we discuss how robust the Hartree-product wavefunction (equation 10) is for computing energies, we need to refine the one-electron Hamiltonian in equation 8. This is required because the one-electron Hamiltonian does not account for the interelectronic repulsion. Computing this potential is not as straightforward because it depends on all possible simultaneous pairwise electron interactions. Thus, the new operator h_i will act on the orbital wavefunction ψ_i :

$$h_i = -\frac{1}{2}\nabla_i^2 - \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{Z_k}{r_{ik}} + V_i\{j\}; \quad V_i\{j\} = \sum_{j \neq i} \int \frac{\rho_j}{r_{ij}} dr \quad (11)$$

where the additional term ($V_i\{j\}$) expresses the electrostatic potential between the electron i with the average charge distribution of the remaining $N-1$ electrons ρ_j . Thus, ρ_j is the charge density of all electrons except electron i at a position r (*mean-field* approach). This takes into account the spread of the wavefunction (unlike the point charges in the second term), hence the integration over all space. This nomenclature of the one-electron Hamiltonian might be confusing since the addition of the new term includes the effect of other electrons (in an average way). The strength of the Hartree products is the ability to divide the many-electron problem into solutions for each single electron Schrödinger equation as shown in equation 10. It gives us more mathematical flexibility, but the “separable” Hamiltonian will not be a good approximation of the true Hamiltonian because each electron interacts with a mean potential generated by other electrons. Hence, their interaction does not account for local effects (known as the mean-field approximation).

2.1.3 Hartree-Fock and Slater Determinants

Until now, the discussion about Hartree-product wave functions has focused on arranging the electrons in a way that minimizes the ground state energy. Nonetheless, we have ignored one main property of electrons, namely spin. The spin quantum number is a natural consequence of relativistic quantum mechanics of electrons. This electron spin function is an eigenfunction that has only two eigenvalues, $\pm\hbar/2$. The spin eigenfunctions are orthonormal and denoted as α and β .

Another principle that the wavefunction should obey is the Pauli exclusion principle, which states that no two electrons can be characterized by the same four quantum numbers. Thus, if two electrons are placed in the same orbital, they must have different spins. For example, the Hartree-product wavefunction of a system consisting of two electrons on a triplet state can be written as in equation 12.

$${}^3\Psi_{\text{HP}} = \psi_a(1)\alpha(1)\psi_b(2)\alpha(2) \quad (12)$$

Here, the two one-electron wavefunctions are different, and the Pauli exclusion principle is held.

Lastly, the Hartree product should account for the antisymmetric nature of the wavefunctions, which means that the sign of the wavefunction should change whenever any two electrons interchange their coordinates. A slight change in the formalism of the Hartree-

product wavefunction should be made to satisfy all the previous constraints (also known as the *electron exchange effects*). This adjustment is to rewrite the wavefunction to satisfy a Slater Determinant, such as:

$${}^3\Psi_{\text{SD}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\psi_a(1)\alpha(1)\psi_b(2)\alpha(2) - \psi_a(2)\alpha(2)\psi_b(1)\alpha(1)] \quad (13)$$

which can also be written in a matrix form

$${}^3\Psi_{\text{SD}} = \begin{vmatrix} \psi_a(1)\alpha(1) & \psi_b(1)\alpha(1) \\ \psi_a(2)\alpha(2) & \psi_b(2)\alpha(2) \end{vmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Although the expressions above consider two electrons and a triplet state, Slater determinants can be written for any other spin multiplicity and any number of electrons.

2.1.4 SCF Procedure

With the concepts discussed above, we can now start discussing more common concepts in the “computational lab.” Firstly, how do we calculate the eigenfunction that corresponds to the minimum energy in a specific state? This is done by the so-called *Self Consistent Field (SCF)*. It is an iterative method developed by Hartree in which an initial guess wavefunction—for organic molecules, Hückel guess is usually a good starting point—of all molecular orbitals is used to construct the one-electron h_i . Then, the corresponding one-electron energy eigenvalues (equation 9) are computed for each electron. New one-electron wavefunctions are generated in each step, which presumably minimizes one-electron energy eigenvalues until a specific criterion, usually the energy, is satisfied. The final wavefunction from the SCF procedure is known as the *converged* wavefunction. It does not necessarily mean that this wavefunction corresponds to the minimum energy of that specific state but rather the wavefunction in which the energy difference between its corresponding energy eigenvalue and the eigenvalue of the next predicted wavefunction is smaller than the energy threshold criteria (iterative limit). The requirements are usually in the order of 10^{-6} to 10^{-8} Hartree (1 Hartree = 27.2114 eV).

Initially, the SCF procedure was used alongside the Hartree-product wavefunction (not the Slater Determinants). The current SCF procedure, on the other hand, is the Fock extension of the Hartree SCF, known as the *Hartree-Fock SCF (HF-SCF)*. Unlike the Hartree-SCF discussed above, the HF-SCF uses the Slater Determinant (SD) wavefunction, meaning that it accounts for anti-symmetry and the Pauli exclusion principle. That is why HF-SCF is the standard procedure when iteratively solving for the energy eigenvalue. The HF method can be considered the basis for computational quantum chemistry methods, which are split into two main categories: Density-based methods and Wavefunction-based methods.

Density-based methods, like the density functional theory (DFT), use electron density in order to find the minimum energy eigenvalue. Although the HF itself can be categorized as a wavefunction-based method, we are referring specifically to the more accurate Post-Hartree-Fock methods, which add the so-called *correlation effect* terms on top of the HF result. The correlation energy is the difference between the exact non-relativistic and the HF energy. It refers to the electronic interaction due to their mutual repulsion that goes beyond the mean-field HF approximation and accounts for the more accurate treatment of electron repulsion and the correlated motion of electrons. Examples of such methods (also known as ab initio post-HF

methods) include Møller–Plesset perturbation theory (MP2),²¹ Couple Cluster Second-Order CC2,²² and Configuration Interaction (CI).²³

2.1.5 Single Reference and Multireference Methods

Until now, we have limited the *converged* wavefunction to being of a single Slater Determinant (single reference). This is usually enough for ground-state calculations, and that is why density functional methods are used; they achieve a good tradeoff between accuracy and computational cost. However, when describing phenomena like dissociation or excited states, using a single SD can be mathematically insufficient due to the nature of the states, which can be thought of as a superposition of multiple SDs. If a single SD can accurately describe the ground state wavefunction, single reference methods are still more or less acceptable. On the other hand, with the ground state wavefunction being only accurately described with multiple SD, single reference methods tend to fail to provide dissociation processes and precise excitations. As such, double excitations (when two electrons are excited simultaneously) take reference states that are required to be of multiple SDs in order to compute them.

Nonetheless, single reference methods are more widely used simply because multireference is usually much more expensive. Examples of single reference methods include Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory (TDDFT) and the Algebraic Diagrammatic Construction to the Second Order ADC(2).²⁴ For multireference, we can cite Multireference Configuration Interaction (MRCI)²⁵ and Complete Active Space Perturbation Theory to second order (CASPT2).²⁶ Singlet Fission (SF) and Singlet-Singlet Annihilation (SSA) are examples of photophysical processes where the use of multireference methods is a must.

2.1.6 Density Functional Theory (DFT)

The non-adiabatic results of this thesis were done at the TDDFT level of theory. Thus, a separate section was dedicated to discussing their formalism. Before discussing Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory, DFT will be briefly presented and contrasted with the Hartree-Fock method.

DFT is a density-based method, meaning that it uses the electron density and correlates it with the eigenvalue of the energy, which, in the case of DFT, is the ground-state energy. This, of course, assumes that all information about a system can be extracted from its density profile. The key strength point of DFT is that this density (function of three coordinates) is way easier to handle compared to the multi-dimensional N -electrons wavefunction that it corresponds to. The term *functional* here means that it is a function of a function, where T and V functions depend on the electron density, which is a function of three-dimensional spatial coordinates. The electron-nuclear attraction energy can be calculated exactly using equation 15. Note that the electron density determines the positions of the nuclei as they appear as local maxima in the electron density since they are effectively point charges.

$$V_{ne}[\rho(r)] = \sum_k^{nuclei} \int \frac{Z_k}{|r - r_k|} \rho(r) dr \quad (15)$$

In DFT language, the electron-nuclei attraction term (equation 15) is known as the external potential because the electrons feel the *external* attraction of all nuclei. Thus, the density

determines the external potential, which determines the Hamiltonian that acts on the wavefunction to find the corresponding energy eigenvalues. This principle is known as the Hohenberg and Kohn principle.²⁷

The Kohn-Sham breakthrough²⁸ was to realize that writing the Hamiltonian operator as a non-interacting system of electrons would considerably simplify the calculations. A Hamiltonian of this type can be represented as a sum of one-electron operators. Its eigenfunctions are Slater determinants formed from the individual one-electron eigenfunctions, and its eigenvalues are merely the sum of the one-electron eigenvalues, as seen in equation 16.

$$\rho = \sum_{i=1}^N \langle \chi_i | \chi_i \rangle \quad (16)$$

where the number of electrons N can be found by integrating the density over all space

$$N = \int \rho(r) dr \quad (17)$$

Since the electrons are described as a density, the electron repulsion (which in this case is self-repulsion) can be described classically as:

$$V_{ee}[\rho(r)] = \frac{1}{2} \int \int \frac{\rho(r_1)\rho(r_2)}{|r_1 - r_2|} dr_1 dr_2 \quad (18)$$

where r_1 and r_2 are dummy variables that span all space. This evaluation of electron repulsion is obviously inaccurate since it implies that electrons feel a repulsion from themselves, which is unphysical. This is usually corrected with the so-called hole function h that compromises this error, as seen in equation 19.

$$\langle \Psi | \sum_{i < j}^{electrons} \frac{1}{r_{ij}} | \Psi \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \int \int \frac{\rho(r_1)\rho(r_2)}{|r_1 - r_2|} dr_1 dr_2 + \frac{1}{2} \int \int \frac{\rho(r_1)h(r_1; r_2)}{|r_1 - r_2|} dr_1 dr_2 \quad (19)$$

The main problem with DFT is that the hole function is not usually able to completely compensate for this error, and that is why DFT usually generates errors regarding the exchange of energy. An example of this is the case of BPW91 (a typical DFT functional), where the total electronic energy of the H atom is $-0.5042 E_h$, but the exact result is -0.5 . Since the H atom is a system with a single electron, this error is then definitely generated from the exchange energy term since the correlation term is zero. Moreover, since the electron density is formed from non-interacting electrons, the expected value of the kinetic energy is also inaccurate.

Usually, the correction to the exchange energy, hole function, correction to kinetic energy, and the correlation effects are summed in the exchange-correlation term, E_{XC} , in the Kohn-Sham formalism, which is written as follows:

$$E[\rho(r)] = \sum_i^N \left(\langle \chi_i | -\frac{1}{2} \nabla_i^2 | \chi_i \rangle - \langle \chi_i | \sum_k^{nuclei} \frac{Z_k}{|r - r_k|} | \chi_i \rangle \right) + \sum_i^N \left(\langle \chi_i | \frac{1}{2} \int \frac{\rho(r')}{|r_i - r'|} | \chi_i \rangle \right) + E_{XC}[\rho(r)] \quad (20)$$

Both DFT and HF rely on the variational principle for the SCF to converge. However, the difference between DFT and HF is that DFT is an exact theory while HF is approximated. This

is because Hartree-Fock uses the mean-field approximation while Density Functional Theory imposes an explicit exchange-correlation term. Ironically, HF equations are solved exactly while DFTs are solved approximately, as we do not know the exact description of E_{XC} term. DFT has become a hot topic for research, as it provides mathematical flexibility and a big room for improvement. A summary of some of the DFT exchange-correlation functional families is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Main DFT approximations for the exchange-correlation functionals.

Functional Name	Description
Local-Density Approximation (LDA)	The functionals are solely affected by the density at the coordinate where it is examined. LDA assumes that the density is constant throughout a molecule. ²⁹
Local Spin-Density Approximation (LSDA)	A straightforward generalization of the LDA to include electron spin. ³⁰
Generalized Gradient Approximations (GGA)	To account for the actual electron density's non-homogeneity, the density gradient is included. This enables adjustments according to density variations distant from the coordinate. ³¹
meta-generalized Gradient Approximations (m-GGA)	In addition to the density and the magnitude of the gradient of the density, a meta-GGA functional employs the Laplacian (second derivative) of the density or the kinetic energy density. ³²
Hybrid Functionals	Hybrid functionals combine exact exchange from Hartree-Fock with DFT exchange-correlation energy. They include LDA, GGA, and exact exchange contributions, improving the accuracy of properties.

The most common hybrid functional in DFT is B3LYP (Becke, 3-parameter, Lee-Yang-Parr).³³ In addition to LSDA electron-electron and electron-nuclei energy, it includes exact exchange and GGA corrections as given in equation 21.

$$E_{XC}^{B3LYP} = (1 - a)E_X^{LSDA} + aE_X^{HF} + b\Delta E_X^B + (1 - c)E_C^{LSDA} + cE_C^{LYP} \quad (21)$$

where E^B and E^{LYP} are both GGA functionals that stand for Becke and Lee-Yang-Parr, respectively. The three first terms are exchange functionals, while the last two are correlation functionals. The addition of an explicit Hartree-Fock term E_X^{HF} compensates for the self-repulsion error in DFT. The coefficients ($a = 0.20$, $b = 0.72$, and $c = 0.81$) are optimized empirically. The Coulomb-attenuated method with B3LYP (CAM-B3LYP) functional has a similar approach to B3LYP. Still, it contains a separation parameter that controls these coefficients (suited for long-range interactions).³⁴

One last point worth mentioning before closing this subsection is the resolution of Identity (RI) approximation, which is a method that accelerates the calculations of two-electron integrals (like the ones in equation 18) using auxiliary basis sets. This approximation has become

standard in some software and is used primarily with DFT functionals and wavefunction-based methods, like MP2.³⁵

2.1.7 Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory (TDDFT)

The Density Functional Theory discussed above can only be applied to the ground state. Excited states, on the other hand, require the wavefunction dependence on time, which should be formulated according to the Time-Dependent Schrödinger equation (TDSE) under a single initial condition:

$$H(t)|\Psi(t)\rangle = i\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi(t)}{\partial t} \quad (22)$$

Similar to DFT, the Runge–Gross theorem in TDSE shows that the density at any time uniquely determines the time-dependent external potential (equation 23).³⁶ For example, the external potential for TDDFT with an external stimulus can be given as:

$$V_{ex}[\rho(r, t)] = \sum_k^{nuclei} \int \frac{Z_k}{|r - R_k(t)|} \rho(r, t) dr \quad (23)$$

The external stimuli (a perturbation) here are characterized by the movement of the nuclei along a classical path. This external perturbation can be an electric or magnetic field. It is worth noting that the Kohn-Sham (KS) formalism for the non-interacting electrons system is also valid with TDDFT. However, in TDDFT, the variational principle is no longer valid. There is, however, a quantity analogous to the energy: the quantum mechanical action. This formalism is not essential in the context of this report and, thus, will not be discussed any further. Instead, it will be replaced by the Linear Response Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory LR-TDDFT.³⁷

Even when using the KS-TDDFT of time-dependent non-interacting electrons, the method is still expensive, even for moderately sized systems. The allure of LR-TDDFT is its ability to produce the exact excitation energies with respect to the exact TDDFT solution. The LR-TDDFT formalism is based on the density change due to a small perturbation (v) turned on at t_0 .

Let us denote the ground state density as $\rho_0(r, t)$, hence, the response function can be written as the Taylor series:

$$\rho(r, t) - \rho_0(r, t) = \rho_1(r, t) + \rho_2(r, t) + \rho_3(r, t) + \dots \quad (24)$$

The numbers here indicate the order of the external perturbation, i.e., linear, quadratic, and so on. The response function (χ) maps the order of the perturbation with the corresponding density.

$$\rho_1(r, t) = \iint \chi(r, t, r', t') v_1(r', t) d^3r' dt \quad (25)$$

For a system of non-interacting electrons, the Kohn-Sham response function is:

$$\chi_{KS}(r, t, r', t') = \left. \frac{\delta \rho[v_{KS}](r, t)}{\delta [v_{KS}](r', t')} \right|_{v_{KS}[\rho_0]} \quad (26)$$

This term defines the exchange-correlation kernel:

$$f_{xc}[\rho_0](r, t, r', t') = \left. \frac{\delta v_{xc}[\rho](r, t)}{\delta \rho(r', t')} \right|_{\rho_0} \quad (27)$$

The exchange-correlation kernel is used to reconstruct the external potential term, in this case, known as the effective potential, that operates on the density ρ_1 and are solved on matrix representation known as the Casida equation.³⁸ The Casida equation is an eigenvalue problem. After diagonalizing the matrix, the lowest eigenvalue gives the first excitation energy, the next gives the second, and so on. The Casida formalism can also be simplified by using the Tamm-Dancoff Approximation (TDA), which neglects the "backward" transitions. In other words, it assumes that the coupling between the electron-hole pairs and their time-reversed counterparts (de-excitations) is negligible.³⁹ This approximation saves a lot of computational cost due to the removal of the \mathbf{B} elements in the Casida equation. TDA performs best when the orbitals are well separated, have significant energy gaps, and most single-electron excitations. It is commonly available in several computational packages, being a default in programs such as ORCA when computing TDDFT excitations.⁴⁰

2.1.8 DFT/MRCI

In this project, multiple methods were used in addition to the primary TDDFT results. However, only DFT/MRCI will be briefly introduced, as it is a less popular method. The DFT/MRCI method (density functional theory and multireference configuration interaction) is a hybrid approach that combines elements from DFT and Configuration Interaction (CI) to improve the accuracy of electronic structure calculations.⁴¹⁻⁴² The DFT/MRCI method offers several advantageous features over TDDFT and wavefunction-based multiconfigurational methods: (i) it can be implemented as a "black box" approach; (ii) it provides high accuracy in vertical excitation energies; (iii) it has a low computational cost (compared to MRCI), making it suitable for large molecules; and (iv) it is capable of describing a wide range of electronic states, including multireference, Rydberg, doubly-excited, and charge transfer states.

DFT/MRCI works by performing a typical DFT calculation, and the resulting ground state KS orbitals are fed to MRCI. As a result, DFT/MRCI is usually sensitive to exchange-correlation functionals. To avoid double counting of electron correlation effects, DFT/MRCI uses a set of parameters to tune the extent to which each method (DFT and MRCI) contributes to the final calculation. This parameterization is specific for each functional. The MRCI method is applied within a chosen active space. It allows for a linear combination of several electronic configurations (spin-adapted combinations of Slater determinants) to accurately describe states with significant multireference character. This calculation refines the wavefunction by including contributions from excited configurations that involve electrons moving between the orbitals in the active space. Thus, the electrons in the orbitals within the active space are treated accurately in terms of their correlation. As a result, since these orbitals are built from multiple configurations, excitation energies are well described by DFT/MRCI.

2.2 Surface Hopping

Surface Hopping is a mixed quantum-classical method for non-adiabatic dynamics in which the electrons are treated quantum mechanically. At the same time, the nuclei are propagated on classical independent trajectories.⁴³ Thus, each trajectory can be thought of as a Born-Oppenheimer trajectory where the electron state can change at each time step, as seen in Figure

3. This state change is known as hopping, and it is controlled by a stochastic process that depends on the hopping probability. At each hopping, the nuclear velocities are adjusted to conserve the total energy. If no velocity adjustment allows the total energy to be kept constant, hopping is not permitted. The flexibility of surface hopping stems from the fact that no global potential energy surfaces are required. Instead, the nuclear geometries at each trajectory are employed to compute all the necessary quantities (on the fly).

Figure 3: Trajectory Energy Representation as a function of Time. The dots represent the actual state at each step. Adapted from Ref 43.

The classical part of surface hopping is an ensemble of independent trajectories that usually are propagated with Newton’s equation of motion on a single adiabatic electronic state J :

$$\frac{\partial^2 R_n}{\partial t^2} = -\frac{1}{M_n} \frac{\partial E_J}{\partial R_n} \quad (28)$$

where E_J is the adiabatic energy of state J , M_n is the mass of the nucleus n , and R_n is its position.

The velocities can, then, be calculated by integrating equation 28, which requires a set of initial positions and velocities. The Verlet algorithm⁴⁴ updates these values at each integration time. There are two ways to calculate hopping probabilities. Global or instantaneous. Global hopping probability assesses the likelihood of a molecule transitioning to a different quantum state after it has crossed and exited a region characterized by nonadiabatic interactions. Zhu–Nakamura model,⁴⁵ for example, is a model to describe global probabilities. The advantage of such a model is that it is not sensitive to non-adiabatic coupling potentials (NACs). However, since the model is derived for specific surface topographies, their reliability in describing an arbitrary molecular system is questionable.⁴³

The instantaneous hopping probabilities, on the other hand, require a detailed description of NACs. The Fewest Switches Surface Hopping (FSSH)⁴⁶ is the most popular algorithm for calculating instantaneous probabilities. This method involves propagating a local approximation of the time-dependent Schrödinger equation for the electronic states. The electronic coefficients derived from this equation are then utilized to estimate the hopping probabilities. Initially, FSSH required nonadiabatic coupling vectors to integrate TDSE. Subsequently, other methods were proposed that do not necessarily satisfy this condition, such as time-derivative couplings computed from wave function overlaps⁴⁷ or energy gaps, as in the time-dependent Baek–An approach.⁴⁸

In FSSH, for electrons, the quantum evolution of motion is used, and the derivative of the wavefunction coefficient c_J with respect to time is described by time-derivative coupling $\sigma_{JK}^{NAC} = \langle \psi_J | \partial / \partial t | \psi_K \rangle$ (where $\psi_{J/K}$ are the electronic wavefunctions of states J and K), and the potential energy E_J at the state J as seen in equation 29. Note that the density matrix ρ could be expressed as $(\rho = c_J c_J^*)$ ⁴⁹

$$\frac{dc_J}{dt} = \sum_K -c_K \left(\frac{i}{\hbar} E_J - \sigma_{JK}^{FSSH-NAC} \right) \quad (29)$$

and the FSSH hopping probability is calculated as:

$$P_{J \rightarrow K}(t) = \max \left[0, -\frac{2\Delta\tau}{|c_J(t)|^2} \sigma_{JK}(t) \text{Re} \left(c_K(t) c_J^*(t) \right) \right] \quad (30)$$

For a hopping to take place ($J \rightarrow K$), the total energy after hopping should be conserved, and the uniform random number r_t between 0 and 1 should follow the inequality:

$$\sum_{L=1}^{K-1} P_{J \rightarrow L} < r_t \leq \sum_{L=1}^K P_{J \rightarrow L} \quad (31)$$

The time-dependent Baek–An (TDBA) approach is considered a balanced method between accuracy and computational time. All dynamics in this thesis were done with TDBA. Thus, a brief introduction to their formalism is introduced.

In TDBA, NAC can be written as:

$$\mathbf{h}_{JK}(t) \equiv \langle \psi_J | \partial / \partial \mathbf{R} | \psi_K \rangle \approx \frac{\text{sgn}(\Delta E_{JK}(t))}{2v_Q} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\Delta E_{JK}(t)} \frac{d^2 \Delta E_{JK}(t)}{dt^2}} \hat{\mathbf{Q}} \quad t \approx t_c \quad (32)$$

where $\Delta E_{JK}(t)$ is the energy difference between the states of interest, $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}$ is a one-dimensional coordinate coupling the adiabatic states J and K , t_c is the crossing time, and v_Q is the projection of velocity in the direction of $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}$.

The time-derivative coupling, $\sigma_{JK}^{NAC} = \mathbf{h}_{JK} \cdot \mathbf{v}$ (where \mathbf{v} is the nuclear velocity), is then

$$\sigma_{JK}^{NAC} = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{sgn}(\Delta E_{JK})}{2} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\Delta E_{JK}} \frac{d^2 \Delta E_{JK}}{dt^2}} & \text{if } \frac{1}{\Delta E_{JK}} \frac{d^2 \Delta E_{JK}}{dt^2} > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } \frac{1}{\Delta E_{JK}} \frac{d^2 \Delta E_{JK}}{dt^2} \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

2.2.1 Initial Conditions

As mentioned above, initial positions and velocities are required to propagate surface hopping trajectories. These quantities, known as initial conditions, are now discussed. The sampling of such quantities is usually done using a harmonic oscillator Wigner Distribution,⁵⁰ which uses the state minimum energy geometry. This distribution assumes that the Potential Energy Surface (PES) is harmonic around the PES (potential well).⁵¹ A potential energy surface describes the energy of a system in terms of specific parameters, usually the position of the

atoms, as shown in Figure 4. The state could be a ground or excited state. The Wigner Distribution is given by

$$P_w(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{P}) = \prod_{i=1}^N \frac{\alpha_i}{\pi \hbar} e^{-\frac{\alpha_i}{\hbar \omega_i} (\omega_i^2 Q_i^2 + P_i^2)} \quad (34)$$

where N is the number of atoms, \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{P} are the mass-scaled coordinate momentum for each normal mode i with reduced mass α_i and angular frequency ω_i . The reduced mass is given in equation 35, where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and T is temperature.

$$\alpha = \tanh\left(\frac{\hbar \omega_i}{2k_B T}\right) \quad (35)$$

After random sampling normal mode coordinates and velocities with these equations, these quantities are converted to Cartesian coordinates and used to initiate the dynamics.

2.3 Excited State Processes

In this subsection, some photochemical processes will be discussed briefly as they will be encountered during the discussion.

Once a molecule is excited, multiple fates are possible. Some of the processes that control these fates are Fluorescence, Phosphorescence, Internal Conversion, and Photochemical reactions (which include bond dissociation, forming, or modification).⁵²⁻⁵³ It is known that most photochemical and photophysical processes occur in the lowest-lying excited states as higher states almost immediately relax in these states.

Photochemical reactions usually occur when there are no efficient relaxation pathways; thus, a molecule tends to break one of its bonds still in the excited state, which can be followed by other chemical reactions. Such a process is usually associated with high-energy activations in the ground state, such as the formation of chlorine radicals from chlorine gas upon excitation with UV light. The chlorine radicals can be used to attack monomers, and a chain reaction is initiated. This process is known as radical polymerization, and it is a widespread method in the plastics industry.⁵⁴ Supermolecules and large extended networks can also undergo photochemical degradation with time, even with low energy excitations due to the generation of reactive species reactive oxygen species (ROS), for example.⁵⁵ The photochemical degradation of organic dyes is very problematic in the photovoltaic industry as they reduce their service times compared to the silicon ones.

To describe fluorescence, we rely on the Franck-Condon interpretation of vertical excitations. According to this principle, electronic transitions occur so rapidly compared to nuclear motions that the positions of the nuclei remain essentially unchanged during the transition. This leads to the concept of vertical excitations between different Potential Energy Surfaces, as exemplified in Figure 4.⁵⁶ Each surface here is a specific electronic state, with the lowest being the ground state. Fluorescence is a spin-allowed process where a molecule absorbs a photon with some specific wavelength and emits radiation with part of this energy. The increase in the wavelength of the emitted photon can be explained by the Franck-Condon principle. A molecule could be excited, let's say, from the ground state minimum geometry to the first excited state. The molecule will rapidly relax to the first excited state minimum geometry via nonradiative vibrational relaxation. A photon is emitted when the molecule

relaxes from S_1 to S_0 , in this case (Figure 4).⁵² Some energy is transferred to the molecule through the vibrational modes as heat; hence, the emitted photon will have less energy. In fluorescent materials, this could be seen as color shifts. For example, a dye could glow blue-green when excited with a UV lamp.

Phosphorescence is also a radiative process, like fluorescence. Still, it involves a change of electronic surface and electron spin (e.g., singlet to triplet). This surface crossing is known as intersystem crossing (ISC). Phosphorescence is a spin-forbidden process that occurs at significantly different time scales compared to fluorescence. This last occurs at time scales between 10^{-9} - 10^{-6} s while phosphorescence occurs at 10^{-3} seconds to even minutes.⁵⁷ As it is a much slower process, studying phosphorescence using surface hopping (which is limited to a few picoseconds) is, in most cases, still not feasible.

Figure 4: Representation of Franck-Condon principle energy diagrams. Adapted from Ref 58.

The last photophysical process to be discussed is internal conversion (IC), which is a nonradiative decay process involving changes between electronic states of the same spin. A fast internal conversion requires efficient relaxation pathways with no or negligible energy barriers (transition states). The energy utilized to overcome these barriers is the kinetic energy gained to compensate for the decrease of potential energy during the vibrational relaxation process in an excited state (as the total energy should be constant).

A conical intersection occurs when there is a crossing between two PESs, which means a crossing between electronic states. Energetically low-lying and barrierless conical intersections provide an accessible and efficient internal conversion relaxation pathway.⁵⁹ In the context of chromophores stability or even the survival of biomolecules, ultrafast internal conversion is a beneficial process that limits photochemical degradation and generation of radical species that could cause DNA mutations or even cancer.⁶⁰ However, in the context of photovoltaics, internal conversion represents a loss mechanism, as the excess energy coming from the absorption is

dissipated as heat before the generation of an electric current, therefore reducing the photovoltaic's efficiency.⁶¹

Conical intersections can be classified as sloped or peaked, describing distinct topological features of the PESs in the vicinity of the state's crossing. This landscape is determined by the relative orientation of the surfaces defined by two vectors, the nonadiabatic coupling and the gradient difference vectors, represented by \mathbf{x}_1 and \mathbf{x}_2 in Figure 5.⁶² In a peaked conical intersection, the topography is sharp, resembling a peak, where the energy rapidly changes in near the intersection point. This type of intersection results in efficient funnels that facilitate rapid internal conversions, often promoting photochemical reactions. Conversely, a sloped conical intersection resembles a slope and features a more gradual inclination in one direction. This gentler gradient results in slower decay processes and more extended regions of state mixing. The nature of the conical intersection—whether peaked or sloped—significantly influences the dynamics of molecular processes such as photochemical reactions and internal conversions.⁵⁹

Figure 5: Possible topologies for conical intersections. Adapted from Ref 63.

3. Photophysics of DPP Dimers

3.1. Introduction to DPP-based Molecules

1,4-diketopyrrolo[3,4-c]pyrroles (DPPs) are chemical pigments that have aromatic systems and can be easily functionalized, as seen in Figure 6. DPP and its derivatives have been used as dyes due to their strong absorption and facility to increase the conjugation length due to functionalization. They also exhibit remarkable photochemical properties, such as incredible fluorescence quantum yields and tunable absorption spectra (up to the 1000 nm region).⁶⁴ Moreover, these cost-effective pigments show high charge-carrier mobilities in conjugated systems with excellent crystallinity and notable thermal and photochemical stability.⁶⁵

Figure 6: Molecular structure of a DPP core and its more common substituents.

Since 2008, DPP-based molecules have been used in organic photovoltaics (OPV) and organic electronics.⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷ The use of DPP as building blocks for high-performance organic semiconductors is promising since the replacement of the functional groups can affordably tune the DPP's absorption spectrum and p-type, n-type, or ambipolar character. DPP-based polymer donors have achieved power conversion efficiencies (PCEs) of a remarkable 9.4%, with broad optical absorption and good film-forming characteristics (good fill factors FF and short-circuit currents J_{sc}).⁶⁶ Currently, the PCE of DPP-containing small molecule donors reaches around 8%.⁶⁷ However, most recently, an outstanding PCE of 12.0% has been achieved.⁶⁵ Besides that, DPP-based small molecules have been shown to be advantageous over their polymer counterparts due to their easier synthesis and their tendency to self-assemble, enhancing their charge carrier mobilities. Yet, higher open-circuit voltage V_{oc} , defined molecular structure, and purification are more manageable with DPP-containing small molecules, as well as less batch-to-batch variation. Moreover, DPP derivatives have also been used to stabilize double-excited states and control internal conversion via manipulation of the side chains.⁶⁸

This urge for interest in the multiple DPP functionalities has motivated us to investigate the photochemistry and photophysics of DPP dimers. The goal was to use this dimer as a prototype for exciton transfer carriers in multichromophoric environments.

3.2 Computational Details

3.2.1 Electronic Structure

Electronic structure calculations were done for the DPP monomer and DPP dimers to investigate the effect of their adjacency. They were done using different methods and packages.

Turbomole V7.6⁶⁹ was used for ground-state calculations at the DFT-B3LYP/def2-TZVP level (geometry optimizations and vibrational frequencies). At the same time, TDDFT-CAM-B3LYP/def2-TZVP was utilized for excited state calculations (geometry optimizations, vibrational frequencies, and excited state properties). The use of DFT-based methods was a good cost-benefit compromise, as multiple guess structures were tested for DPP dimers in the search for the most stable conformer for the ground state geometry. The resolution of Identity (RI) approximation was used as implemented in Turbomole. Long-range dispersion interactions (van der Waals forces) were accounted for using the DFT-D4 dispersion correction model.⁷⁰ Nudged Elastic Band (NEB) was used in ORCA 5.0.4^{40, 71} to calculate the minimum energy path between the geometries of interest.

At the beginning of the project, additional calculations were done using CC2 (Turbomole v7.6), DFT/MRCI (DFTCI program),^{41, 72} and ODM3/MRCI (MNDO program)⁷³ in order to benchmark excitation energies. These results are only presented in the Annexes.

The wavefunction analysis was done using TheoDORE software.⁷⁴ Natural transition orbitals (NTOs), charge transfer (CT), and average position of the excitation (POS) calculation were investigated.

3.2.2 Initial Conditions

Three main sets of dynamics were performed: two sets starting from the S_1 minimum, one for the unsubstituted DPP core ($R = R_1 = H$ in Figure 6) and another set for a functionalized DPP ($R = CH_3$ in Figure 6); a third set starting from the S_0 minimum of the unsubstituted DPP.

The first two used Wigner distribution around the S_1 -minimum calculated with the def2-SV(P) basis set. The vibrational frequencies evaluated numerically in the first excited electronic state were computed using the NumForce program in Turbomole. These simulations intended to probe excitation near the excitation band origin. Apart from the basis set, which was reduced to cut the computational costs, all the remaining settings of the calculations were kept the same to generate 100 sampling points using Newton-X Classical Series (NX-CS)¹⁶ and Turbomole v7.6. Thus, 100 trajectories were generated as no filtering criteria were needed. The two dynamics here differ only by functionalizing the DPP dimer to suppress the hydrogen transfer conical intersection, which will be discussed later. As a remark, in this chapter, we refer to the crossing between electronic states as conical intersections. Nevertheless, we should bear in mind that, at the TDDFT level, the branching space surrounding the intersection between S_0 and S_1 state has a dimensionality of one, not two.⁷⁵ Therefore, those intersection points are not rigorously conical at this theoretical level.

The primary purpose of the third dynamic was to study the relaxation pathway of the non-functionalized DPP dimer after vertical excitation near the excitation band maximum. To do so, 500 initial conditions were generated from a Wigner distribution around the S_0 -minimum calculated using DFT-B3LYP/6-31G**. This basis set was used to add polarization functions (p-type functions) on hydrogen atoms. TDDFT-CAM-B3LYP/TDA/6-31G** was employed to compute vertical excitation energies for the sampling points. In this set, the initial conditions were generated using ORCA 5.0.4 software⁴⁰ due to some reasons that will be discussed in the next section. The geometries were then filtered by choosing the excitation energy centered at the maximum absorption wavelength (3.5 ± 0.2 eV). This selected window (shown in Figure 7)

resulted in a ratio of 41:84 accepted geometries for the first and second excited states, respectively. A total of 120 trajectories were generated, obeying the 1:2 proportion between $S_1:S_2$.

Figure 7: Simulated absorption spectra of DPP calculated using CAM-B3LYP/6-31G**. The shaded area indicates the spectral window from where the initial conditions for the dynamics were selected.

3.2.3 Surface Hopping

The dynamics were propagated using Newton-X CS interfaced with the ORCA package due to its stability and efficiency.

It was reported that surface hopping at the TDDFT level interfaced with Turbomole could result in multiple crashed trajectories. Such a problem has not been reported when using ORCA.⁷⁶ Moreover, ORCA calculations are faster than the corresponding calculations done with Turbomole. The reason can be attributed to the state-of-the-art RIJCOSX used by the former, which is a more efficient version of the Resolution of Identity. A short benchmark study using ORCA and Turbomole was performed to verify this statement. All the parameters were kept the same between the two programs, except the RIJCOSX and the DFT-grid size, as, according to ORCA developers, they are “completely re-optimized by machine-learning techniques and should be more robust.”⁴⁰ The results show that 30 single-point calculations using the same arbitrary trajectories finished in 85.85 minutes in Turbomole compared to 77.55 with ORCA. Although these results cannot be entirely decisive, as a supercomputer facility was used and not all CPUs are equal on it, we opted to proceed using ORCA.

The Fewest Switches Surface Hopping (FSSH) method was employed, incorporating decoherence effects with the simplified decay of mixing⁷⁷ using $\alpha = 0.1$ Hartree. All the dynamics included three states (ground plus two excited states). The TDA approximation was used as it shows a good tradeoff between accuracy and computational cost, and it performs better for dynamics than TDDFT.⁷⁸⁻⁷⁹ The dynamics were run up to 1 picosecond, using a classical step size of 0.5 femtosecond; hence, a maximum of 2000 single-point calculations were performed per trajectory. The TDSE was integrated with a timestep of 0.025 fs, with electronic properties interpolated between the classical steps.

The set with the initial conditions selected from the S_1 minimum was calculated at TDDFT-CAM-B3LYP/6-31G*; the third set of dynamics uses a 6-31G** basis set, as explained above. Besides that, a more significant difference between the sets is that the latest adjusts the velocity after hopping using the reduced kinetic energy protocol⁸⁰ (where the kinetic energy is divided by the number of degrees of freedom), while the first two use full kinetic energy. This procedure is discussed in Ref 80 and used in order to avoid an artificial excess of back hoppings. In the three cases, the momentum remained unchanged in cases of frustrated hoppings.

3.3 Results and Discussion

3.3.1 Static Results

Prior to investigating the dynamics of the DPP dimers, it is helpful to discuss the electronic properties of the isolated monomer. Thus, we will first discuss the low-lying excited state of the monomer and compare them to the DPP dimer.

The core of the DPP molecule (without functionalization) is shown in Figure 8. The optimization of the ground state returns a planar geometry. The normal modes were calculated to confirm the absence of imaginary frequencies; the IR spectrum is shown in Figure S1.

Figure 8: Molecular structure of DPP monomer.

Vertical excitation energies of DPP-monomer using TD-DFT (CAM-B3LYP) are shown in Table 2 (Table S1 using CC2). It can be noted that the excitations are a mix of $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n_O \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The first excited state is the brightest and corresponds to a HOMO to LUMO transition.

Table 2: DPP-monomer vertical excitations calculated with CAM-B3LYP/def2-TZVP.

State	Transition	E_{exc} [eV]	f_{osc}	λ [nm]
S ₁	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.56	0.257	348.36
S ₂	$n_O \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.12	0.000	301.29
S ₃	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.12	0.000	301.09
S ₄	$n_O \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.58	0.000	270.44
S ₅	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	5.52	0.000	224.80
S ₆	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	6.51	0.000	190.45

State	Hole	Electron	Coefficient
S_1		0.7677	
S_2		0.0542	
		0.9148	
S_3		0.9608	
S_4		0.1118	
		0.8568	

Figure 9: NTOs for the DPP monomer at the S_0 minimum (level CAM-B3LYP/def2-TZVP).

The corresponding Natural Transition Orbitals (NTOs) for these transitions are shown in Figure 9. Here, only four states are shown, as the high-energy transitions are not crucial for excitations into the first band. It can be observed that the lone pairs of the oxygen are the ones responsible for the $n_O \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions, while the lone pairs of nitrogen participate in the π -conjugation.

Next, the minimum energy geometry of the DPP dimer was investigated. This can be a bit tricky, as many different molecular orientations are possible. Thus, multiple guess structures based on different atomic positions were investigated. At the DFT level, the geometry with the smaller energy was the guess 2 of Table 3 (the guess 6 converged to the same geometry). The guess structures are a mix of multiple typical configurations like π -stacking, T-shape, glide plane, and so on, as seen in Figure S2. No imaginary frequencies were observed on guess 2,

confirming that it is a global minimum, as seen in Figure S3. The same procedure was also done at CC2, as shown in Table S3. The CC2 results agree with the DFT ones.

Table 3: Relative energies of optimized DPP-dimer starting from different guess structures. Calculations were done at CAM-B3LYP/def2-TZVP.

Structure	DFT [eV]
Guess 1	0
Guess 2	-0.3837
Guess 3	-0.3455
Guess 4	-0.3455
Guess 5	-0.3455
Guess 6	-0.3836

The optimized guess 2 structure is shown in Figure 10, and it will be referred to as the DPP dimer from now on. Two things can be noticed here. First, the two monomers are not entirely planar anymore due to the interaction between the oxygens in one monomer and the hydrogens of the amine groups in the other monomer; the second observation is that the dimer is decoupled due to the orientation of the chromophores (which do not present typical π -stacking geometries but an almost perfect perpendicular face-to-face orientation). This can be seen in Table 4 as the excitation energies are duplicated, implying the degeneracy of states. Nonetheless, the two chromophores are non-covalently interacting, which is manifested in that the total electronic energy of the dimer is 0.63 eV less than twice the energy of the monomer (-981.915558 vs. $2 \times (-490.946131)$ Hartree).

Figure 10: Molecular structure of the S_0 state of the DPP-dimer (frontal and side view) and atom numbering.

Table 4 shows the vertical excitation energies computed at the TDDFT level. These calculations were repeated with different methods, including DFT/MRCI, ADC(2), and ODM3, and are shown in Table S4. These comparisons confirm that CAM-B3LYP can adequately describe this dimer. The first excited state of the dimer is 0.15 eV smaller than that of the dimer (3.41 vs. 3.56 eV).

Table 4: DPP-dimer vertical excitations at CAM-B3LYP/def2-TZVP level.

State	Transition type	E_{exc} [eV]	f_{osc}	λ [nm]	MO Transitions
S ₁	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.41	0.111	363.27	70->71
S ₂	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.41	0.111	363.21	69->71
S ₃	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.70	0.072	334.88	70->72
S ₄	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.70	0.072	334.83	69->72
S ₅	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.05	0.000	306.29	68,66->71,72
S ₆	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.07	0.000	304.77	68,66->72,71

The NTOs of the dimer (Figure 11) show that each transition in the first four excited states is delocalized into the two chromophores. This indicates the existence of a π -interaction, which is responsible for the interaction between the chromophores and, thus, its charge transfer character.

Figure 11. NTOs for the DPP dimer at the S₀ minimum (level CAM-B3LYP/def2-TZVP).

The relaxation process in the S₁ involves changes in the molecular conformation of the dimer, which is accompanied by a decrease in the first excited state energy. At the S₁ minimum, we notice that now the HOMO is localized in a single monomer unit. In contrast, the LUMO is localized over the other monomer unit. This indicates the formation of a charge transfer (CT) state or a CT exciton. The S₁ geometry is characterized mainly by a change in the improper

dihedral angle between the chromophores (atoms 1-5-14-15) from 50° in S_0 minimum to about 33° in S_1 minimum. This change corresponds to a relative rotation between the two molecules, which favors the N-H-O interaction in the first excited state (as can be observed comparing Figure 10 and Figure 12). The orbitals involved in the first excited state of the S_1 minimum are shown in Figure 13. The S_1 minimum geometry is confirmed by the absence of imaginary frequencies, as shown in Figure S4.

Figure 12. Molecular structure of the DPP-dimer optimized in the S_1 state (frontal and side view) and atom numbering.

Figure 13. NTOs for the DPP dimer at the S_1 minimum (level CAM-B3LYP/def2-TZVP).

The molecular relaxation from the vertical excitation region to the first excited state is more efficient in the DPP dimer compared to the DPP monomer (0.49 eV compared to 0.16 eV). This means that the dimer could gain more kinetic energy (compared to the monomer) via relaxation through the vibrational modes. Such energy can be used to overcome energy barriers (transition states) to other photochemical processes.

The vertical transitions from S_0 and S_1 minimum using TDDFT and other methods are shown in Table S11. Since the chromophores in the DPP dimer are identical, two energetically identical S_1 -minima states exist with opposite electron-hole positions, as shown in Figure 14. The intermediate geometries here were generated using linear interpolation. The transition state and the intermediate, precisely in the middle, show the degeneracy of the states. Thus, depending on the exact energy of the dimer and the environmental influence, the excitation energy could be localized in one of the chromophores. The orbitals shown in Figure 14 are the HOMOs just to differentiate between the chromophore's states. The invalidity of Marcus's

theory in calculating the electron transfer rate of our particular system is discussed in the Appendix.

Figure 14. Linear interpolation alongside the two degenerated S_1 minima for the DPP-dimer.

3.3.2 Dynamics

Dynamics were done using a smaller basis set (6-31G* or 6-31G**) compared to the static calculations discussed in the previous section to save computational time. Therefore, first of all, it is essential to show that the approximation used will maintain the reliability of the calculations. Table 5 shows the vertical excitations calculated for the lowest excited states incorporated in the dynamics. The results with the two basis sets used for the dynamics agree with each other. Thus, they can be thought of as equivalent levels, except for the velocity adjustment mentioned in section 3.2.3. The vertical excitations, on the other hand, show some differences when compared with triple zeta/TDDFT calculations. In this case, the excitation energies are ~ 0.13 eV smaller, but this is within the error margin for TDDFT methods. The oscillator strengths show more significant differences by a factor of one-third. Fortunately, these divergences are not problematic because the most important is not a perfect agreement between those numbers but rather the relative differences between them. In this view, we can notice that the three datasets show the degeneracy of S_1 and S_2 , which have the same energies and oscillator strength. Moreover, nonadiabatic couplings and their corresponding hopping probabilities are not directly proportional to oscillator strengths. Thus, we conclude that the settings used for dynamics are compatible with the results discussed in the static calculations.

After confirming the reliability of the levels of theory used, we can confidently discuss the DPP-dimer results in terms of population analysis. These results are shown in Figure 15 and are meant to discuss the relaxation pathways. Thus, the analysis is done with the dynamics from the Wigner distribution around the S_0 minima and not for the sets based on the S_1 minima. This is because the kinetic energy gained by relaxing to the S_1 minima will determine which energy

barriers can be overcome before fully relaxing to the ground state. The excited state population shown here is the sum of the population of both the first and second excited states. The full relaxation from S_2 to S_1 occurs within only 20 fs, as shown in Figure S7. The population is not calculated as a fraction of trajectories on a specific state. Still, the sum of all populations and all trajectories is normalized to the number of trajectories.

Table 5: Comparison between the vertical excitations computed for DPP-dimer with different methods.

Methods	TDDFT/def2-TZVP		TDDFT/TDA/6-31G*		TDDFT/TDA/6-31G**	
	Energy [eV]	f_{osc}	Energy [eV]	f_{osc}	Energy [eV]	f_{osc}
S₁	3.41	0.111	3.54	0.034	3.53	0.033
S₂	3.41	0.111	3.54	0.034	3.53	0.034

We can see in Figure 15 that the excited state population at the end of the dynamics (1 ps) is less than 15%, implying that the exciton lifetime is too short to be used in photovoltaics, which for organic solar cells can reach the nanosecond regime.⁸¹ Such a short lifetime indicates that this DPP-dimer is not even a fluorescence, which is surprising since DPP derivatives and DPP crystals are reported to be strongly fluorescent in the literature.⁸²⁻⁸³ To examine the cause of such a short lifetime, we need to investigate the geometries during hopping times.

Figure 15. Population's evolution for the DPP-dimer starting from S_0 -minima.

Table 6 shows the statistics for the 120 trajectories in terms of hopping geometries. Only 8 (6.7%) trajectories were still in the excited states at the end of the dynamics, which shows the strong coherence between the states since the population at the end of the analysis was about 14%. The hoppings to the ground state were divided into four main pathways. The first is hydrogen migration from the amino group to the oxygen atom in the other monomer. This hopping is due to a conical intersection, as the hopping geometries have almost zero $S_1 - S_0$ energy gap (dE). It is clearly the dominant relaxation process of about 92 trajectories (76.7%).

Second, we observed what we call stochastic hoppings, characterized by having dE of more than 1 eV and no abnormal geometries (geometries that are not typically of conical intersections). They are due to the stochastic nature of the surface hopping process. Hopping happens if the randomly generated number is smaller than the hopping probability at that specific time step. The hopping probability at hopping time was checked, and the probability was small. This means that we cannot decisively confirm whether those hoppings were artificial or not. The stochastic hoppings made up 15% of the trajectories, which is statistically significant. The last two categories of hoppings, involving CH-O interaction and CH bond breaking, are minor results (< 2%) and can be ignored.

Table 6: Classification of the trajectories in terms of hopping geometries. dE is the $S_1 - S_0$ energy gap.

Type of Trajectory	$S_1 - S_0$	Counts	%
Survived	-	8	6.7
Hydrogen migration CI	$dE \approx 0$	92	76.7
Stochastic	$dE > 1$	18	15
CH-O interaction	$dE > 1$	1	0.8
CH bond breaking	$dE > 1$	1	0.8

Since the H migration conical intersection (or simply hydrogen conical intersection) is the main relaxation pathway, extra analysis will be provided to complement the results. Figure 16 shows the population analysis discussed previously and includes a histogram showing the hopping time distribution due to the hydrogen conical intersection. If we look carefully at the excited state's population decay, we see two distinct processes responsible for this decay. The fast decay is due to H conical intersection, and a slow decay is primarily attributed to the stochastic process. The fact that the slow decay feature is extended across the whole dynamics time is not surprising since that is the nature of such a process. The histograms shown in Figure 16 indicate two things. First, the relaxation through hydrogen migration requires some time to be triggered, in this case around 280 fs. This will be discussed later when comparing the other dynamics. Second, this process has a constant rate, as the histograms are approximately the same height.

Figure 16: Hopping distribution for the DPP-dimer starting from S_0 -minima.

We found that a single exponential or a multiexponential decay function was not a good fit for the population decay. This is mainly because the population decay is triggered after a certain time. Before this time, excited-state intermediates are formed. This is the nature of a sigmoid function, which has an S-shape. In contrast, the exponential function has a continuously decreasing curve. Sigmoid decay is not something usually used to describe the decay of photochemical processes. Still, there are examples in the literature that have similar observations, such as for coumaryl Meldrum and sinapoyl Meldrum⁸⁴ and other systems.⁸⁵⁻⁸⁶ The sigmoid function is given by:

$$p(t) = \frac{a}{1 + e^{\frac{t-\tau_L}{\tau_E}}} \quad (36)$$

and its fit is shown in Figure 17.

For numerical stability of the fitting algorithm, the x-axis was recalled to ps, and the y-axis was adjusted to be in the interval [0,1]. The time constant τ_L was found to be 348 fs, which is the time at which half of the population is relaxed to the ground state. During the hydrogen migration conical intersection, the population decay follows the time constant of τ_E . Before decaying to the ground state, an excited state minimum is formed at the time $\tau_L - \tau_E$, that means around 300 fs. Thus, the internal conversion lifetime τ_{IC} at which the population decay is decreased by a factor of a $1/e$ can be calculated as

$$\tau_{IC} = \tau_E \ln(e - 1) + \tau_L \quad (37)$$

The error margin can be calculated as

$$\delta\tau = Z \frac{s}{\sqrt{N}} \quad (38)$$

where $Z=1.96$ is the value of the normal distribution with a 95% confidence interval. N is the number of trajectories, and s is the standard deviation of a logistic model, which can be found as:

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\pi^2 \tau_E^2}{3}} \quad (39)$$

Thus, the internal conversion lifetime is 427 ± 26 fs.

Figure 17. Sigmoid fitting of the excited state population decay.

The geometry corresponding to the conical intersection is shown in Figure 18. It can be observed that the geometry is very similar to S_1 minimum in terms of the orientation angle between the chromophores and differs in terms of O-H bond formation, as shown in Figure 12. This means that the 300 fs required to trigger the relaxation pathway will include the time to relax from S_0 to S_1 minima. Of course, this time is not precise since we statistically start from the Wigner distribution around the S_0 minima, and that is why the hopping time extends as tail after 500 fs, as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 18: Hopping structure of DPP-dimer characterized as H-conical intersection.

To understand how accessible the hydrogen conical intersection relaxation pathway is, its potential energy surface is plotted in Figure 19. This pathway was calculated using the Nudged Elastic Band (NEB) method to find the minimum energy pathway between S_0 minimum and S_1 minimum and between S_1 minimum and the conical intersection. The transition state was optimized and confirmed to have a single imaginary frequency corresponding to the hydrogen migration. Mass-weighted distances were used to quantify the degree of differences between the initial structure and the corresponding intermediates. It can be observed that the molecule has more than enough energy to overcome this barrier since the dissipative (kinetic) energy gained by relaxing from the S_0 minimum to the S_1 minimum is 0.65 eV. In comparison, the activation energy is only 0.04 eV. The same PES was constructed with the bigger def2-TZVP basis set, and a similar result was obtained.

Figure 19: PES along the H-conical intersection relaxation as a function of the mass-weighted distance. Calculated with TDA/CAM-B3LYP/6-31G**.

Wavefunction characterization. Until now, the conical intersection has been regarded as a hydrogen conical intersection even though we have not discussed whether it is a hydrogen or a proton transfer. To confirm this, we tracked the NTOs along the pathway presented in Figure 19. This analysis showed a proton transfer following an electron transfer. Therefore, since a proton and an electron are transferred, the process is a hydrogen transfer. This type of transfer is well-known, being named either proton-coupled electron transfer (PCET)⁸⁷ or electron-driven proton transfer (EDPT).⁸⁸

Moreover, we have characterized the wavefunction along the pathway using the TheoDORÉ program. TheoDORÉ uses the transition density matrix to calculate descriptors such as charge transfer (CT) and average position of excitation (POS). The equations governing both are discussed in the Appendix. Both descriptors require the indication of specific fragments involved in the exciton transfer. Here, the two fragments are each one of the chromophores, but those fragments were updated after the hydrogen migration. The CT value ranges from zero to 1, where 0 indicates no charge transfer, and 1 indicates one electron transfer. POS, on the other hand, varies from one to two. If the number is close to one or two, it suggests an intra-excitation within the same monomer. In contrast, a value around 1.5 shows an inter-excitation between the fragments or a transition with the hole and electron delocalized in the whole dimer. We have performed CT and POS for the first two excited states. These results, with their corresponding energies along the reaction pathway, are shown in Figure 20.

Let us first focus on POS and CT for the first excited state. We can observe that POS-S₁ is constant along the pathway. This is because the transition of the first excited state is characterized by an inter $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition between the chromophores. Hence, the average value is 1.5. Nonetheless, we see a dip in the first point (S₀ minimum) where the POS-S₁ slightly shifts to fragment one. This is because, in this case, the LUMO is not fully localized in one chromophore. Thus, there is more contribution from one chromophore than the other (Figure 21). This dip in the S₀ geometry is reversed in S₂ since the states are degenerate. One can see

that the CT number increases along the PES, which is close to 1 at the conical intersection. This implies that almost an entire electron is transferred at the end of the reaction coordinate, which means that one hydrogen is being transferred rather than a proton. POS, on the other hand, does not tell us much, in this case, as it remains close to 1.5 during the whole coordinate. This means that the average exciton position remains between the two fragments along the reaction coordinate, which makes sense, as the hole and electron are localized in different fragments along the whole pathway.

We also noted that this dip exists in the CT- S_1 , and it is frankly underestimated based on our previous static calculations. We expected that the CT- S_1 value in the first geometry (S_0) would be smaller than 0.89. If we check the NTOs in Figure 11, we can see that the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition is completely delocalized in the two chromophores; thus, a CT smaller than 0.5 would be expected, which indicates a local excitation (LE). However, as can be seen in Figure 20, this value is much larger (0.890).

Figure 20: POS (A) and CT (B) calculated along the PES for the H-conical intersection (calculated with TDA/CAM-B3LYP/6-31G**)

When trying to understand those differences, we found some interesting results. We first checked if this would be related to the different basis sets used in the static calculations (TDDFT-def2-TZVP) and in the dynamics and NEB calculations (TDA-6-31G**). Even though Kohn-Sham orbitals are very similar in the two basis sets, their corresponding NTOs are different (Figure 21). In the first case, the hole and electron are entirely delocalized in the two fragments; in the other case, the hole and electron are localized in different fragments. This results in very different CT numbers (0.44 vs. 0.89). When we increased the basis set to def2-TZVP, the problem persisted. However, when we turned off the TDA approximation, we got CT numbers consistent with our initial static calculations; that is, the S_1 excitation has a localized character (LE). This means that setting $\mathbf{B} = 0$ in the Casida equations can alter the NTOs. This is because all contributions to the excitation energies coming from the de-excitation of the correlated ground state are neglected.

Regarding the second excited state, we observe that it is energetically close to the third excited state during almost the whole PES. However, both states are irrelevant to us since they are about 1 eV higher than S_1 , which dictates the deactivation pathway in the dynamics. It is worth mentioning that the role of hydrogen in this conical intersection is not to change the orbital involved in the excitation but rather to shorten the energy difference between S_0 and S_1 . We can see this in the dramatic change in CT- S_2 around the transition state.

Level	S1-h	S1-e	S2-h	S2-e	CT	POS
def2-TZVP TDDFT					S1 0.440	1.385
					S2 0.443	1.614
6-31G** TDA					S1 0.89	1.468
					S2 0.89	1.533
6-31G** TDDFT					S1 0.586	1.374
					S2 0.583	1.629

Figure 21: NTO, CT, and POS numbers calculated for the S_1 state at the S_0 geometry with different approaches and basis sets.

Dynamics of substituted Me-DPP. Figure 22 shows the three dynamics of the DPP dimer and DPP dimer functionalized with methyl groups (Me-DPP). Comparison between the green (Me-DPP dimer) and red (DPP dimer) curves shows how the methyl functionalization is efficient in

suppressing the hydrogen conical intersection, which is evident as the substituent blocked this pathway. However, we still observe a decay to the ground state. In this case, however, this was uniquely due to the stochastic nature of the surface hopping method.

Although the hopping probability at the hopping times shows that TDBA gives no abnormal results, we cannot fully confirm whether this decay is artificial or not. Such a confirmation will require a complete set of new dynamics with a different method using nonadiabatic couplings.

We can compare the two mentioned curves with the blue decay (dynamics starting from the S_0 minimum distribution). Still, we must be careful since this curve uses reduced kinetic energy for velocity adjustment. In contrast, the previous uses full kinetic energy, as discussed in Ref 80. Quantitatively speaking, starting from the ground state geometry gives more energy available to the molecules to overcome the barrier and populate the ground state; thus, the conversion would happen more rapidly and to a higher extension degree.

It is worth mentioning that we observed hopping geometries other than H-conical intersection or stochastically in the two sets centered at S_1 minima (red and green) but not in the one centered in the S_0 minima (blue). However, those are minor pathways and will not be discussed here as they do not add much to the analysis of DPP internal conversion. An example of such conical intersections is the formation of a covalent bond between the molecules involving one of the oxygens (see Figure S6). A possible reason why they were present is the Wigner distribution, which generates conformations and velocities that will give rise to more energetic structures. It can also be observed that the three curves have the same slope of the stochastic decay even though they were done with different basis sets.

Figure 22: Summary of the S_1 population decay for the three sets of dynamics. Red and blue curves are for DPP dimer and sampled from S_1 and S_0 minima, respectively. Green is Me-DPP dimer sampled from S_1 minima.

3.4 Conclusion on DPPs

In this thesis, the initial objective was to study exciton transport in nanostructure molecular systems. To do so, a diketopyrrolopyrrole (DPP) dimer was used as a prototype due to its applications in photovoltaics and organic semiconductors. To our surprise, our dynamic calculations show distinct photophysics from what is expected for a strongly fluorescent dye, as DPP is reported. Our excited state nonadiabatic dynamics report short-living excited states with an internal conversion lifetime of 427 ± 26 fs. This was caused by a barrierless hydrogen migration conical intersection. As such, this relaxation pathway contributed to more than 75% of the total trajectories that relaxed to the ground state. The population decay of the excited state was observed to follow a logistic model. The decay to the ground state was triggered by the transfer of hydrogen between the two chromophores at the hopping time, attributed to the presence of a conical intersection. Quantitatively, we could confirm that the initial plateau in the population decay curve is due to conformational relaxation from the initially excited S_0 to the S_1 minima. This ultrafast decay pathway was suppressed when we changed the hydrogen in the amide group to a methyl group. Thus, we conclude that the functionalization of DPP small molecules is very crucial to avoid internal conversion at early times and sustain favorable photophysical properties for its use in organic photovoltaics.

Our wavefunction analysis along the pathway shows that there is a full hydrogen migration rather than a proton transfer, indicated by a CT value closer to 1, especially close to the conical intersection. Moreover, POS has shown that the dimer exhibits an average exciton position close to the medium distance between the two chromophores along the pathway. Starting from the S_0 minimum, we observe a local excitation, which immediately vanishes as the dimer approaches the S_1 minimum. We report that this local excitation is suppressed when the calculations are done with the TDA approximation, as noted from the natural transition orbitals and CT numbers. Nevertheless, this does not affect the result of our dynamics, since it was using Beack-AN approximation, which uses only energy gap and second derivatives of the energy gaps.

In conclusion, we confirm the successful completion of this thesis. Nonetheless, in the next chapter, we discuss a side project that was investigated simultaneously. This project concerns singlet-singlet annihilation (SSA). Still, we faced many challenges in investigating SSA, which are reported as a perspective in the following chapter.

4. SSA: Challenges and Perspectives

The initial goal of this project was to investigate Singlet-Singlet Annihilation (SSA) in a DPP dimer. However, we faced many challenges in this process. In this chapter, our attempts to study SSA are discussed, including the challenges and possible solutions that could be implemented in the future.

SSA is a process that can occur when two molecules, both in an excited singlet state, interact with each other. Still, one of them is promoted to a higher singlet state while the other returns to the ground state. In this process, the energy from the molecule that returns to the ground state is transferred to the other molecule, allowing it to jump to a higher excited state, from where it rapidly returns to the S_1 (Figure 23). As it competes with energy transfer, this process can decrease the efficiency of photovoltaics by 50% due to the reduction of charge carriers.¹⁴

Figure 23: Singlet-singlet annihilation process.

We have seen in the previous Chapter that the DPP dimer exhibits two degenerate states corresponding to the first and second states. These can be referred to as $|S_1\rangle$ and $|S_2\rangle$ of the dimer. At the S_1 minimum geometry, most of the excitation is localized on a specific monomer, as can be seen in Figure 13. As there are two degenerated states, there will be two equivalent S_1 minima, with the hole and electron interchanged between the two chromophores (see Figure 14). If we think about this representation in terms of the chromophores $|S_1\rangle$ and $|S_2\rangle$ of the dimer as $|S_1S_0\rangle$ and $|S_0S_1\rangle$.

In our previous discussion, we have limited the photochemical process to a single excitation, i.e., a single electron is elevated to a higher energy level. But what if we want to study the DPP dimer while two electrons are excited into the same orbital? This will originate what we represent by $|S_1S_1\rangle$ state. In this case, one electron in each one of the chromophore is excited to the S_1 state. Thus, if there is a SSA, this state could evolve to originate $|S_0S_n\rangle$ or $|S_nS_0\rangle$, where n is an integer larger than 1 and represents a higher excited state.

The $|S_1S_1\rangle$ state is a double excited state, which requires a multireference method to be described. Thus, TDDFT cannot be used anymore, as it is a single reference state and cannot describe multiple excitations. Moreover, unfortunately, using a high-end method like CASPT2 or MRCI is still not feasible due to their high computational demand, especially if surface

hopping is needed. Therefore, we are left with few options. An affordable choice was to use a semiempirical multireference method.

The semiempirical multireference method chosen was OM3/MRCI,⁸⁹ which is a standard MRCI procedure that uses ODM3/MRCI molecular orbitals. ODM3/MRCI is a type of OMx method known as *orthogonalization corrected methods* that account for repulsive orthogonalization effects, attractive penetration effects, and repulsive core-valence interactions via explicit corrections.⁹⁰⁻⁹² This is different from the MNDO-type methods, which ignore such corrections. ODM3 will not be discussed extensively here, but a few remarks could be made. ODM3 includes the dispersion correction not just as an energy correction but by re-parametrizing the Hamiltonian to describe the noncovalent interactions better. Furthermore, ODM3/MRCI was parametrized with a diverse set of molecules to train both ground and excited states.⁸⁹ The dispersion corrected added here is Grimme’s dispersion correction⁹³ with Becke–Johnson (BJ) damping function.⁹⁴

Table 7 shows the vertical excitation energies of the DPP dimer using ODM3/MRCI. Although the excitation energies are obviously overestimated compared to ADC(2), TDDFT, and DFT/MRCI methods (see Table S4), they are not as problematic as the existence of the double excitation (state 5) lacking in the other three methods. The numbers (12/10) shown in Table 7 describe the active space chosen, given the number of occupied and virtual orbitals, respectively. Apparently, the doubly excited states, represented in red in the Table 7, are energetically too low compared to twice the energy of $|S_1\rangle$ (7.72 vs. 4.24 eV).

Table 7: DPP Dimer vertical excitations at ODM3/MRCI(12,10) level.

State	Transition	E_{exc} [eV]	f_{osc}	λ [nm]	MO Transitions
ODM3/MRCI (12/10) geometry optimized with (5/3)					
S₁	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.86	0.331	320.93	50,49->51
S₂	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.87	0.334	320.62	49,50->51
S₃	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.13	0.000	300.42	48,47->51,52
S₄	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.15	0.000	298.78	47,48->51,52
S₅	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.24	0.000	292.35	49,50->51 D
S₆	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.39	0.033	282.28	50->52

Before we proceed, we need to address some of the challenges faced when using MNDO, the software used for ODM3/MRCI calculations. Walter Thiel and co-workers wrote the MNDO program, which offers a wide range of calculations.^{90-91, 95} Unfortunately, the program has not had much technical support over the years. Until now, it can only be used with a single-core computer. In our calculations, we observed that most crashes happen due to *segmentation fault*, which is a specific kind of error that occurs when a program requires more memory than is available to operate. It is often the problem with methods relying on active spaces, as the memory requirements increase exponentially with the active space. Yet, the wrong choice of active space can result in completely unreliable results. For example, Table 8 shows different combinations of active space and their corresponding calculations for DPP monomer and dimer.

Only two active spaces give reasonable results to optimize the S_1 minimum for the DPP monomer, which are 5/3 and 10/4.

On the other hand, only the 5/3 active space was able to optimize the DPP in the ground state without error. This was concerning since the active space was too small for a dimer. Other combinations (from DFT/MRCI suggestions) were used, but the problem has persisted.

Table 8: Performance of different active spaces for DPP-monomer and dimer. The energies reported are the S_1-S_0 energy gap at the S_1 optimized geometry with each active space tested for the monomer. For the dimer, "No" stands for crashed calculations with segmentation error for the S_0 optimizations.

Active Space (Occupied/Virtual)	Monomer S_1-S_0 gap [eV]	Dimer S_0 Optimization
12/6	0.000050	No
8/4	0.000004	No
7/4	0.000038	No
6/4	0.003162	No
5/3	3.646856	Yes
17/9	1.607550	No
10/4	3.657029	No

Figure 24 shows the geometry of the DPP dimer S_1 minimum optimized with different methods. It can be seen that ADC(2) and TDDFT show similar results ($|S_1S_0\rangle$ and $|S_0S_1\rangle$), while ODM3/MRCI using (5/3) shows the wrong geometry even when the segmentation error did not occur. The hypothesis was that the small active space was responsible for this error. Still, the problem is that if the active space were to be increased, segmentation errors would occur.

Figure 24: S_1 minima geometry using different methods.

Different approaches were used to increase the active space above the segmentation limit, including calculating the gradients of only a specific state and not calculating non-adiabatic coupling matrix elements. This allowed us to increase the active space up to (12/10). However, vertical excitations become problematic. Thus, we were left with no choice but to deactivate the *mciref=3* option in the MNDO input file. This option means that the calculation starts with the reference occupations chosen by default and adds further references so that their fraction in all configuration interaction (CI) roots is at least 85%. After that, the CI calculation is repeated once. This option is usually strongly recommended since it ensures the correct number of CI references and helps with wavefunction convergence. However, this option implies a more costly calculation, which was responsible for the segmentation fault errors. After deactivating this option, an active space benchmark study was done, and we achieved spaces as large as (17/16).

Table 9 shows the excitations for the DPP dimer using the new highest active space (17/16). It can be noted that ODM3/MRCI fails to capture the degeneracy between the first and second excited states, raising additional problems. The geometry used in this table was the same geometry for both ODM3/MRCI and DFT/MRCI. We observed the double excitation in both methods (S_6 with ODM3/MRCI and S_7 with DFT/MRCI). To our surprise, the problem was not strictly due to ODM3/MRCI, as initially thought. To investigate this further, we analyzed the double excitation as a function of distance between the monomers.

Table 9: DPP Dimer vertical excitations computed with ODM3/MRCI(17,16) and DFT/MRCI(def2-TZVP). The doubly excited state is highlighted in blue. The different orbital numbering is due to the *frozen core* approach used in ODM3/MRCI.

State	E_{exc} [eV]	f_{osc}	λ [nm]	MO Transitions
ODM3/MRCI (17/16) Dimer				
S_1	3.82	0.223	325	50>51
S_2	4.22	0.230	294	49->51
S_3	4.52	0.000	275	48->51
S_4	4.73	0.000	262	47>51
S_5	4.75	0.051	261	50->52
S_6	4.77	0.000	260	49,50->52
DFT-MRCI(def2-TZVP)				
S_1	2.96	0.135	419	70->71
S_2	3	0.166	413	69->71
S_3	3.38	0.113	367	70->72
S_4	3.43	0.091	361	69->72
S_5	3.61	0.000	343	68->71
S_6	3.64	0.001	341	66->71
S_7	3.67	0.000	338	69,70->71

To study the interaction as a function of distance, we describe the dimer using the optimized geometry of the two monomers ODM3(10/10) (not the relaxed geometry of the dimer). The

distance between the monomers varied between 3 and 8000 Å. All the calculations were done with ODM3/MRCI, but some points were done with DFT/MRCI as well. Due to some concerns about the segmentation fault errors, we used a relatively small active space (10/10). The vertical excitations for the monomer are shown in Table S2. For the dimer, they are shown from Table S5 to Table S10. It can be observed that both ODM3/MRCI and DFT/MRCI show the same low-lying double excitations. Their corresponding orbitals were also checked to make sure that we were observing the same state for all distances between the monomers.

It is worth mentioning that the excited electrons in the double excitation were elevated to the same orbital for the geometries where the distance between the monomers was between 3 and 4 Å, but excited to different orbitals in the other geometries. ODM3/MRCI and DFT/MRCI present the doubly excited state in a different order (different number of the state), but this is not the most relevant. The main problem is that both fail to adequately describe the state of interest along the whole distance. This failure may stem from the fact that they are both built based on the configuration interaction method, which has a documented history of size consistency problems.⁹⁶⁻⁹⁷ Nevertheless, we still try to optimize the S_1 minimum of the dimer with the highest active space possible for ODM3/MRCI, but this has also failed due to Segmentation fault error.

To study the SSA, however, we do need to optimize the doubly excited state, which, unfortunately, was not possible. Moreover, the double excitation state can change its numbering during the optimization. Hence, MNDO may not track this state, leading to a different state.

In their publication, the authors report that the ODM3/MRCI method fails to differentiate between covalent and noncovalent O–H bonds in carboxylic acid dimers. Although the DPP dimer does not have a carboxyl group, it has secondary amide groups. Despite the large difference in acidity of these two functional groups (tendency to lose the proton) we suspect that this could be one of the reasons why ODM3/MRCI was unable to describe our system. From all the reasons explained above, we concluded that semiempirical methods like MRCI based on ODM3 and ODM2 fail to describe the system, being inappropriate for investigating SSA. DFT/MRCI has also shown some errors and, above that, does not provide gradients for geometry optimization capabilities. One alternative would be to use the more expensive CASPT2-based methods, which should not show similar size consistency problems. This, of course, will increase the computational cost sensationally, but it could shed some light on the SSA process.

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ANNEXES

A. Static Calculations: DPP Monomer

Table S1: DPP monomer vertical excitations with CC2 method.

State	Transition	E_{exc} [eV]	f_{osc}	λ [nm]
S1	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.45	0.298	359.25
S2	$n_O \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.79	0.000	326.95
S3	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.89	0.000	318.96
S4	$n_O \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.25	0.000	291.46
S5	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	5.28	0.000	234.84
S6	$n_O \rightarrow \pi^*$	6.17	0.000	201.04

IR Spectrum

Figure S1: DPP monomer IR spectrum.

Table S2: Vertical Excitations of DPP monomer with ODM3/MRCI (10/10).

State	E_{exc} [eV]	$f_{osc-length}$	λ [nm]	MO Transitions
ODM3/MRCI (10/10) monomer				
S1	3.57	0.283	347	25->26
S2	3.83	0.000	323	24->26
S3	3.93	0.002	316	23->26
S4	4.18	0.000	296	25->28
S5	4.31	0.000	288	22>26
S6	4.68	0.000	265	25->29
S7	4.73	0.000	262	25->27

B. Static Calculations: DPP Dimer

Figure S2: DPP dimer guess structures for DFT optimizations.

Table S3: Relative energies between the DPP dimer optimized guess structures with CC2.

Structure	CC2 [eV]
Guess 1	0
Guess 2	-0.444
Guess 3	-0.013

IR Spectrum

Figure S3: DPP dimer IR spectrum.

Table S4: DPP dimer vertical excitations summary.

State	Transition	E_{exc} [eV]	f_{osc}	λ [nm]	MO Transitions
ADC(2)					
S₁	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.09	0.178	401.52	70->71
S₂	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.09	0.179	401.52	69->71
S₃	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.53	0.025	351.27	70->72
S₄	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.53	0.025	351.25	69->72
S₅	$n_o/\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.55	0.000	349.17	65,66->71,72
S₆	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.74	0.000	331.36	67,68->71,72
ODM3/MRCI (12/10)					
S₁	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.86	0.331	320.93	50,49->51
S₂	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.87	0.334	320.62	49,50->51
S₃	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.13	0.000	300.42	48,47->51,52
S₄	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.15	0.000	298.78	47,48->51,52
S₅	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.24	0.000	292.35	49,50->51 D
S₆	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.39	0.033	282.28	50->52
TD-DFT					
S₁	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.41	0.111	363.27	70->71
S₂	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.41	0.111	363.21	69->71
S₃	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.70	0.072	334.88	70->72
S₄	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.70	0.072	334.83	69->72
S₅	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.05	0.000	306.29	68,66->71,72
S₆	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	4.07	0.000	304.77	68,66->72,71
DFT/MRCI geometry optimized with DFT					
S₁	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.24	0.212	383	70->71
S₂	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.24	0.213	383	69->71
S₃	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.52	0.056	352	70->72
S₄	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.52	0.055	352	69->72
S₅	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.76	0.001	330	66,65->71,72
S₆	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	3.76	0.000	330	65,66->71,72

IR Spectrum

Figure S4: DPP dimer IR spectrum for S_1 minimum.

Table S5: Vertical excitations for DPP dimer with the chromophores separated by 3Å. The doubly excited state is represented in blue. The different orbital numbering is due to the *frozen core* approach used in ODM3/MRCI.

State	E_{exc} [eV]	f_{osc}	λ [nm]	MO Transitions
ODM3/MRCI (10/10) Dimer 3Å				
S₁	3.96	0.385	313	50->51, 49->51
S₂	3.99	0.421	311	49->51, 50->51
S₃	4.27	0.000	290	50,49->51 D, 50,49->52 D
S₄	4.39	0.000	283	48->51, 47->52
S₅	4.41	0.000	281	47->51, 48->52
S₆	4.53	0.024	273	50->52
S₇	4.57	0.021	271	49->52
DFT/MRCI				
S₁	2.96	0.135	419	70->71
S₂	3	0.166	413	69->71
S₃	3.38	0.113	367	70->72
S₄	3.43	0.091	361	69->72
S₅	3.61	0.000	343	68->71
S₆	3.64	0.001	341	66->71
S₇	3.67	0.000	338	69,70->71 D

Table S6: Vertical excitations for DPP dimer with the chromophores separated by 4Å. The doubly excited state is represented in blue. The different orbital numbering is due to the *frozen core* approach used in ODM3/MRCI.

State	E_{exc} [eV]	f_{osc}	λ [nm]	MO Transitions
ODM3/MRCI (10/10) Dimer 4Å				
S ₁	4.03	0.42	308	50>52, 49->51
S ₂	4.05	0.47	306	49->51, 50>52
S ₃	4.29	0.000	289	50,49->51 D, 50,49->52 D
S ₄	4.45	0.000	279	48->51
S ₅	4.47	0.000	277	47->52
S ₆	4.59	0.000	270	50->56
S ₇	4.64	0.002	267	45->51
DFT/MRCI				
S ₁	3.14	0.266	395	70->71,72
S ₂	3.15	0.299	394	69->71,72
S ₃	3.53	0.000	351	69,70->71,72
S ₄	3.58	0.005	346	70->71,72
S ₅	3.65	0.000	340	69->71,72
S ₆	3.67	0.000	338	65->71,72
S ₇	3.69	0.000	336	66->72

Table S7: Vertical excitations for DPP dimer with the chromophores separated by 8Å. The doubly excited state is represented in blue. The different orbital numbering is due to the *frozen core* approach used in ODM3/MRCI.

State	E_{exc} [eV]	f_{osc}	λ [nm]	MO Transitions
ODM3/MRCI (10/10) Dimer 8Å				
S ₁	4.05	0.448	306	50>52
S ₂	4.05	0.482	306	49->51
S ₃	4.29	0.000	289	49,50->51,52 D
S ₄	4.47	0.000	278	48->51
S ₅	4.49	0.000	276	47->52
S ₆	4.59	0.000	270	50->56
S ₇	4.62	0.002	268	45->51

Table S8: Vertical excitations for DPP dimer with the chromophores separated by 44 Å. The doubly excited state is represented in blue. The different orbital numbering is due to the *frozen core* approach used in ODM3/MRCI.

State	E_{exc} [eV]	f_{osc}	λ [nm]	MO Transitions
ODM3/MRCI (10/10) Dimer 44Å				
S ₁	4.05	0.468	306	50->52
S ₂	4.05	0.470	306	49->51
S ₃	4.29	0.000	289	49,50->51,52 D
S ₄	4.47	0.000	278	48->51
S ₅	4.50	0.000	276	47->52
S ₆	4.58	0.000	271	50->56
S ₇	4.62	0.002	269	45->51

Table S9: Vertical excitations for DPP dimer with the chromophores separated by 400 Å. The doubly excited state is represented in blue. The different orbital numbering is due to the *frozen core* approach used in ODM3/MRCI.

State	E_{exc} [eV]	f_{osc}	λ [nm]	MO Transitions
ODM3/MRCI (10/10) Dimer 400Å				
S ₁	4.5	0.468	306	50->52
S ₂	4.05	0.470	306	49->51
S ₃	4.29	0.000	289	49,50->51,52 D
S ₄	4.47	0.000	278	48->51
S ₅	4.50	0.000	276	47->52
S ₆	4.58	0.000	271	50->56
S ₇	4.62	0.002	269	45->51
DFT/MRCI				
S ₁	3.22	0.348	385	69->71
S ₂	3.22	0.349	385	70->72
S ₃	3.44	0.000	360	69,70->71,72 D
S ₄	3.74	0.000	331	65->71
S ₅	3.77	0.000	329	66->72
S ₆	3.86	0.000	321	68->71
S ₇	3.91	0.000	317	67->72

Table S10: Vertical excitations for DPP dimer with the chromophores separated by 8000 Å. The doubly excited state is represented in blue. The different orbital numbering is due to the *frozen core* approach used in ODM3/MRCI.

State	E_{exc} [eV]	f_{osc}	λ [nm]	MO Transitions
ODM3/MRCI (10/10) Dimer 8000Å				
S₁	4.05	0.468	306	50>52
S₂	4.05	0.470	306	49->51
S₃	4.29	0.000	289	49,50->51,52 D
S₄	4.47	0.000	278	48->51
S₅	4.50	0.000	276	47->52
S₆	4.58	0.000	271	50->56
S₇	4.62	0.002	269	45->51

Table S11: DPP dimer vertical transitions summary from S₀ and S₁ minimum.

Method	S ₀ -m[eV]	S ₁ -m[eV]
Monomer		
CC(2)	3.45	3.13
TD-DFT	3.56	3.21
ODM3/MRCI (5/3)	3.84	3.66
DFT/MRCI (TD-DFT optimized geometry)	3.39	3.08
Dimer (guess 2)		
ADC(2)	3.09	2.08
TD-DFT	3.41	2.26
ODM3/MRCI (5/3)	4.05	3.76
DFT/MRCI (TD-DFT optimized geometry)	3.24	2.20

C. Static calculations: Me-DPP dimer

Figure S5: Molecular structure of Me-DPP dimer.

Figure S6: Example of a Me-DPP hopping geometry (5 trajectories).

D. Dimer's dynamics: DPP dimer

Figure S7: Excited state population evolution for set 3 of dynamics (starting from the S_0).

In the report, the effect of using solvent that could suppress the H conical intersection wasn't discussed. Although it is known in nonadiabatic dynamics that implicit models, like CPCM-SMD,⁹⁸ are not capable of suppressing such a process, we run some exploratory trajectories including implicit solvation and a smaller basis set (3-21G), seen in Figure S8. These results confirm these predictions. Note that those dynamics have only an exploratory character and, therefore, are not extensively discussed.

Figure S8: The effect of an implicit solvent (exploratory 3-21G Dynamics) for the DPP dimer.

E. Comparison Between Orca and Turbomole Results

A comparison between ORCA and Turbomole results is shown in Figure S9. This figure displays the energy evolution for a single trajectory. The relative differences between S_0 and S_1 in each respective method are the same. However, the energies computed with the two programs are slightly different because the two programs do not have the same grid size used in the DFT calculations.

Figure S9: Energy evolution for a single trajectory computed with CAM-B3LYP/def2-SV(P) using Orca and Turbomole.

Nonetheless, if each program was normalized to its respective energy, the curves match perfectly as seen in Figure S10. The only difference here is that in these 30 single-point calculations, ORCA was 8.3 minutes earlier.

Figure S10: Normalized energy evolution for a single trajectory computed with CAM-B3LYP/def2-SV(P) using Orca and Turbomole.

APPENDIX

A. Wavefunction Characterization

The characterization of excitation along the H migration pathway in DPP was done with TheoDORÉ program. Some of the relevant equations will be given here.

Consider a system consisting of multiple fragments. The localized orbital basis of the transition matrix element for a transition from the ground state to the n th excited state can be calculated as:

$$D_{ab}^{0n} = \langle 0 | \hat{\mathcal{E}}_{ab} | n \rangle \quad (40)$$

where $\hat{\mathcal{E}}_{ab}$ is an excitation operator for the orbitals a and b localized as fragments A and B, respectively. Thus, a charge transfer number Ω_{AB}^n for an excitation can be defined as:

$$\Omega_{AB}^n = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu \in A} \sum_{\nu \in B} [(D^{0n} S)_{\mu\nu} (S D^{0n})_{\mu\nu} + D_{\mu\nu}^{0n} (S D^{0n} S)_{\mu\nu}] \quad (41)$$

where S represents the orbital overlap matrix. This value indicates the contribution of charge transfer from fragment A to fragment B (when $A \neq B$), and the contribution from excitations within the same fragment (when $A=B$). The total charge transfer character for a system with multiple fragments is defined as:

$$CT = \frac{1}{\Omega^n} \sum_A \sum_{B \neq A} \Omega_{AB}^n \quad (42)$$

with Ω^n representing the total sum of the charge transfer values for all pairs A and B.

We can also introduce the position of the excitation (POS) as:

$$POS = \frac{\sum_A A (\sum_B \Omega_{AB}^n + \Omega_{BA}^n)}{2\Omega^n} \quad (43)$$

This quantity represents the localization of the transition. POS assume values between 1 and 2. If $POS = 1$, it means that the transition is completely localized in the chromophore 1 (hole and electron are in the same chromophore); if $POS = 2$, the transition is completely localized in the chromophore 2. Intermediary values imply a delocalized transition (either hole and electron localized in different chromophores or both, hole and electron, delocalized in the dimer).

B. Marcus Theory

Marcus's theorem was shown to be invalid in describing our particular system. A brief discussion about it will be provided here.

Marcus's theory is used to explain the electron transfer reaction rates between donors and acceptors described by:

Marcus's theory uses the coupling between two potential energy surfaces along a reaction pathway, as depicted in Figure S11. Equation 41 shows the rate of electron transfer according to Marcus's¹³ theory (without the theory refinement).

$$k_{et} = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} |H_{AB}|^2 \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi\lambda k_B T}} e^{\left(-\frac{(\lambda + \Delta G^\circ)}{4\lambda k_B T}\right)} \quad (45)$$

where H_{AB} is the coupling potential, k_B is Boltzmann's constant, λ is reorganization energy and, T is temperature. λ can be calculated from:

$$\Delta G^\circ = \frac{(\lambda + \Delta G^\ddagger)^2}{4\lambda} \quad (46)$$

where ΔG^\ddagger is the energy barrier. For a system of identical monomers (a decoupled dimer), the theory could be misleading. First, the energy degeneracy will not facilitate the electron transfer because the theory does not take into account the density overlaps between the reactants and the products, which (in this case) are spatially different. Moreover, since we have an energy degeneracy, H_{AB} tends to zero and the rate is also zero, indicating another inconsistency.

Figure S11: Schematics for Marcus's Theory for electron transfer reactions.